

Improvement of production of alkaloid and flavonoid compounds in *Narcissus tazetta* L. callus under iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄-NPs) and trans-cinnamic acid and L-phenylalanine treatments

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Abstract

The medicinal properties of the *Narcissus* genus are due to the presence of alkaloids known as Amaryllidaceae Alkaloids (AA), especially in the bulbs of this plant. In this study, the effect of iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe₃O₄-NPs), trans-cinnamic acid (*t*CA), and L-phenylalanine (L-Phe) as precursors have been investigated on changes in some biochemical parameters of *Narcissus tazetta* L. callus, especially alkaloid content. The results showed that when calli induced on the bulb explants in Murashig-Skoog (MS) media containing 2,4-D and BAP treated with Fe₃O₄-NPs, secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds increased significantly. Also, the activity of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and peroxidase (POD), and the activity of some enzymes such as phenylalanine ammonia-lyase (PAL) and tyrosine ammonia-lyase (TAL) increased under Fe₃O₄-NPs treatments alone and in combination with *t*CA or L-Phe precursors. The evaluation of the studied parameter changes showed that both *t*CA and L-Phe treatment can change the plant's metabolism to improve the production of secondary metabolites. This was especially evident with the simultaneous application of Fe₃O₄-NPs and these precursors. Application of precursors in the culture medium increased H₂O₂ content under *t*CA treatment and decreased it under L-Phe treatment. Increased activity of the antioxidant enzymes caused by nanoparticle treatments along with the nutritional effect of *t*CA and L-Phe precursors, progressed the signaling pathway of antioxidant responses by affecting the activity of biosynthetic enzymes and increasing the production of some secondary metabolites including alkaloids and phenolic compounds.

Keywords: Amaryllidaceae Alkaloids, Fe₃O₄-NPs, *Narcissus tazetta* L., Phenylalanine, trans-cinnamic acid.